

*Transplant Games***17th National Transplant Games
by Narmada Kidney Foundation****Bharath V Shah**

Gleneagles Hospital, Mumbai, India

Dr. Bharat V. Shah

Director, Institute of Renal Sciences,
Gleneagles Hospital, Mumbai
Director, Advanced Transplant Diagnostics
and Immunogenetics
Gen. Secretary, ZTCC, Mumbai
Managing Trustee, Narmada Kidney Foundation
Past-President, Indian Society of Nephrology, West Zone
Past-President, Mumbai Nephrology Group

Narmada Kidney Foundation (NKF) is a registered Non-Governmental Organization (NGO) set up in 1993 to create awareness about kidney diseases, organ donation and transplantation. One of its major activities is to conduct national transplant games every year.

The transplant games aim to show how transplant recipients return to normalcy after transplant. In the past, transplant games were conducted sporadically in India. Narmada Kidney Foundation (NKF) is the first organization in the country to consistently organize National Transplant Games (NTG) from 2008. This year was the 17th NTG.

The NTG show how people with organ failure live life to their fullest after transplant. Besides transplant recipients, living donors who have donated kidney or part of the liver also participate in the NTG to show that they continue to remain as normal after donation as they were before donation. This creates huge confidence among potential transplant recipients and donors.

This year, the National Transplant Games supported by the Indian Society of Organ Transplantation (ISOT) and Ghatkopar Jolly Gymkhana saw participation of about 300 living donors and transplant recipients from different parts of the country. The games were held at Ghatkopar Jolly Gymkhana and inaugurated by Dr. Sanjay Kolte, President of ISOT. Also present were Dr. Bipin Chevale, CEO, Gleneagles Hospitals, Parel, Mumbai, Shri Rajnikant Shah, Chairman, Ghatkopar Jolly Gymkhana and the committee members of Ghatkopar Jolly Gymkhana.

The Games started with lighting of Torch by Dr. Bharat Shah, founder member and managing trustee of NKF. The torch was then passed on to the donors and recipients, representing shared journey of life, hope and survival through organ donation and transplantation.

The event brought together heart, liver, kidney, and even hand transplant recipients, showcasing their strength and resilience. Living donors who donated kidneys or a part of their liver also participated in the games. The Games featured events like relay running, pickle ball, box cricket, badminton, table tennis, carom and chess. A new game Petanque was also introduced this year.

These games are very important for transplant recipients and donors as well. You get to know your potential and when you come here you get inspired by seeing so many people doing various activities which you thought you never would after transplant said Mr. Digvijay Singh (Jabalpur, Madhya Pradesh). He had his kidney transplant in 2011 and is a regular participant in NTG. The NTG inspired him to participate and represent India in world transplant games in Newcastle in 2019 and Perth in 2023.

Mr. Bhagwan Reddy and Mr. Hitesh Soni who participated thanked NKF for organizing these games.

Sixty-seven years old Shaikh Ansa Khasam who underwent liver transplant in 2013, with his son as donor, showcased his incredible skill and perseverance in the carom competition.

The event ended with prize distribution ceremony where winners from various competitions were honoured for their prize winning performances. Medals and certificates were presented to the winners.

This celebration served as a beacon of hope for thousands and strengthened the message of organ donation and transplantation, said Mr. Dnyanraj Patkar, a transplant recipient himself and president of Narmada kidney Foundation.

Corresponding Author: Dr. Sunil Shroff,
MOHAN Foundation, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India
Email: shroff@mohanfoundation.org

To cite : Shah B V. 17th National Transplant Games by Narmada Kidney Foundation. Indian Transplant Newsletter. 2024 Oct-Dec; 23(4):p5.

